

Target	Common name	Uniprot ID	ChEMBL ID	Target Class	Probability*	Known actives (3D/2D)
NADPH oxidase 4	NOX4	Q9NPH5	CHEMBL1250375	Enzyme		7 / 8
Vasopressin V2 receptor	AVPR2	P30518	CHEMBL1790	Family A G protein-coupled receptor		1 / 1
Aldose reductase	AKR1B1	P15121	CHEMBL1900	Enzyme		18 / 72
Xanthine dehydrogenase	XDH	P47989	CHEMBL1929	Oxidoreductase		12 / 20
Monoamine oxidase A	MAOA	P21397	CHEMBL1951	Oxidoreductase		4 / 14
Insulin-like growth factor I receptor	IGF1R	P08069	CHEMBL1957	Kinase		3 / 3
Tyrosine-protein kinase receptor FLT3	FLT3	P36888	CHEMBL1974	Kinase		5 / 7
Cytochrome P450 19A1	CYP19A1	P11511	CHEMBL1978	Cytochrome P450		5 / 18
Epidermal growth factor receptor erbB1	EGFR	P00533	CHEMBL203	Kinase		5 / 28
Thrombin	F2	P00734	CHEMBL204	Protease		11 / 3
Carbonic anhydrase II	CA2	P00918	CHEMBL205	Lyase		7 / 15
Serine/threonine-protein kinase PIM1	PIM1	P11309	CHEMBL2147	Kinase		7 / 7
Arachidonate 5-lipoxygenase	ALOX5	P09917	CHEMBL215	Oxidoreductase		5 / 46
Serine/threonine-protein kinase Aurora-B	AURKB	Q96GD4	CHEMBL2185	Kinase		3 / 4
Dopamine D4 receptor	DRD4	P21917	CHEMBL219	Family A G protein-coupled receptor		1 / 1
Adenosine A1 receptor (by homology)	ADORA1	P30542	CHEMBL226	Family A G protein-coupled receptor		6 / 23
Carbonic anhydrase VII	CA7	P43166	CHEMBL2326	Lyase		8 / 14
Glyoxalase I	GLO1	Q04760	CHEMBL2424	Enzyme		3 / 4
Myeloperoxidase	MPO	P05164	CHEMBL2439	Enzyme		1 / 1
PI3-kinase p85-alpha subunit	PIK3R1	P27986	CHEMBL2506	Enzyme		1 / 1
Adenosine A2a receptor (by homology)	ADORA2A	P29274	CHEMBL251	Family A G protein-coupled receptor		5 / 11
Death-associated protein kinase 1	DAPK1	P53355	CHEMBL2558	Kinase		2 / 2
Liver glycogen phosphorylase	PYGL	P06737	CHEMBL2568	Enzyme		1 / 1
Carbonic anhydrase I	CA1	P00915	CHEMBL261	Lyase		3 / 5
Glycogen synthase kinase-3 beta	GSK3B	P49841	CHEMBL262	Kinase		3 / 6
Tyrosine-protein kinase SRC	SRC	P12931	CHEMBL267	Kinase		2 / 10
Focal adhesion kinase 1	PTK2	Q05397	CHEMBL2695	Kinase		1 / 2
Estradiol 17-beta-dehydrogenase 2	HSD17B2	P37059	CHEMBL2789	Enzyme		8 / 3
Vascular endothelial growth factor receptor 2	KDR	P35968	CHEMBL279	Kinase		2 / 3
Matrix metalloproteinase 13	MMP13	P45452	CHEMBL280	Protease		1 / 1
Matrix metalloproteinase 3	MMP3	P08254	CHEMBL283	Protease		1 / 1
Carbonic anhydrase III	CA3	P07451	CHEMBL2885	Lyase		1 / 1
Arachidonate 15-lipoxygenase	ALOX15	P16050	CHEMBL2903	Enzyme		4 / 8
Multidrug resistance-associated protein 1	ABCC1	P33527	CHEMBL3004	Primary active transporter		7 / 11
Serine/threonine-protein kinase PLK1	PLK1	P53350	CHEMBL3024	Kinase		2 / 3
Carbonic anhydrase VI	CA6	P23280	CHEMBL3025	Lyase		1 / 1
Cyclin-dependent kinase 1	CDK1	P06493	CHEMBL308	Kinase		2 / 13
Matrix metalloproteinase 9	MMP9	P14780	CHEMBL321	Protease		2 / 2
Carbonic anhydrase XII	CA12	O43570	CHEMBL3242	Lyase		8 / 17
Matrix metalloproteinase 2	MMP2	P08253	CHEMBL333	Protease		2 / 2
Protein kinase N1	PKN1	Q16512	CHEMBL3384	Kinase		1 / 3
Carbonic anhydrase XIV	CA14	Q9ULX7	CHEMBL3510	Lyase		1 / 1
Carbonic anhydrase IX	CA9	Q16790	CHEMBL3594	Lyase		3 / 5
Casein kinase II alpha	CSNK2A1	P68400	CHEMBL3629	Kinase		3 / 2
Arachidonate 12-lipoxygenase	ALOX12	P18054	CHEMBL3687	Enzyme		5 / 10
Hepatocyte growth factor receptor	MET	P08581	CHEMBL3717	Kinase		2 / 4
Carbonic anhydrase IV	CA4	P22748	CHEMBL3729	Lyase		7 / 13
Serine/threonine-protein kinase NEK2	NEK2	P51955	CHEMBL3835	Kinase		1 / 2
Interleukin-8 receptor A	CXCR1	P25024	CHEMBL4029	Family A G protein-coupled receptor		1 / 1
CaM kinase II beta	CAMK2B	Q13554	CHEMBL4121	Kinase		1 / 2
ALK tyrosine kinase receptor	ALK	Q9UM73	CHEMBL4247	Kinase		2 / 4
Serine/threonine-protein kinase AKT	AKT1	P31749	CHEMBL4282	Kinase		1 / 4
P-glycoprotein 1	ABCB1	P08183	CHEMBL4302	Primary active transporter		11 / 48
Serine/threonine-protein kinase NEK6	NEK6	Q9HC98	CHEMBL4309	Kinase		1 / 2
Phospholipase A2 group 1B	PLA2G1B	P04054	CHEMBL4426	Enzyme		1 / 1
Carbonic anhydrase VA	CA5A	P35218	CHEMBL4789	Lyase		1 / 1
Beta-secretase 1	BACE1	P56817	CHEMBL4822	Protease		8 / 14
Cytochrome P450 1B1	CYP1B1	Q16678	CHEMBL4878	Cytochrome P450		12 / 46
Tyrosine-protein kinase receptor UFO	AXL	P30530	CHEMBL4895	Kinase		2 / 4
ATP-binding cassette sub-family G member 2	ABCG2	Q9UNQ0	CHEMBL5393	Primary active transporter		6 / 50
NUAK family SNF1-like kinase 1	NUAK1	O60285	CHEMBL5784	Kinase		1 / 2
Aldo-keto reductase family 1 member C2 (by homology)	AKR1C2	P52895	CHEMBL5847	Enzyme		1 / 1
Aldo-keto reductase family 1 member C1 (by homology)	AKR1C1	Q04828	CHEMBL5905	Enzyme		1 / 1
Aldo-keto reductase family 1 member C3 (by homology)	AKR1C3	P42330	CHEMBL4681	Enzyme		1 / 1
Aldo-keto reductase family 1 member C4 (by homology)	AKR1C4	P17516	CHEMBL4999	Enzyme		1 / 1
Carbonic anhydrase XIII (by homology)	CA13	Q8N1Q1	CHEMBL3912	Lyase		1 / 1
Aldehyde reductase (by homology)	AKR1A1	P14550	CHEMBL2246	Enzyme		1 / 1
G-protein coupled receptor 35	GPR35	Q9HC97	CHEMBL1293267	Family A G protein-coupled receptor		2 / 4
Microtubule-associated protein tau	MAPT	P10636	CHEMBL1293224	Unclassified protein		1 / 1
Lysine-specific demethylase 4D-like	KDM4E	B2RXH2	CHEMBL1293226	Eraser		2 / 2
DNA topoisomerase II alpha	TOP2A	P11388	CHEMBL1806	Isomerase		1 / 1
Insulin receptor	INSR	P06213	CHEMBL1981	Kinase		1 / 1
Acetylcholinesterase	ACHE	P22303	CHEMBL220	Hydrolase		4 / 27
Myosin light chain kinase, smooth muscle	MYLK	Q15746	CHEMBL2428	Kinase		1 / 1
Tyrosine-protein kinase SYK	SYK	P43405	CHEMBL2599	Kinase		3 / 3
PI3-kinase p110-gamma subunit	PIK3CG	P48736	CHEMBL3267	Enzyme		3 / 1
DNA-(apurinic or apyrimidinic site) lyase	APEX1	P27695	CHEMBL5619	Enzyme		1 / 1
Receptor-type tyrosine-protein phosphatase S	PTPRS	Q13332	CHEMBL2396508	Phosphatase		6 / 8
Estrogen receptor beta	ESR2	Q92731	CHEMBL242	Nuclear receptor		62 / 29
DNA-3-methyladenine glycosylase	MPG	P29372	CHEMBL3396943	Enzyme		1 / 1
Solute carrier family 22 member 12	SLC22A12	Q96S37	CHEMBL6120	Electrochemical transporter		4 / 1
Cyclin-dependent kinase 5/CDK5 activator 1	CDK5R1 CDK5	Q15078 Q00535	CHEMBL1907600	Kinase		6 / 18
Cyclin-dependent kinase 1/cyclin B	CCNB3 CDK1 CCNB1 CCNB2	Q8WWL7 P06493 P14835 Q05067	CHEMBL2094127	Other cytosolic protein		4 / 9
Arginase-1 (by homology)	ARG1	P05089	CHEMBL1075097	Enzyme		2 / 2
Cyclin-dependent kinase 6	CDK6	Q00534	CHEMBL2508	Kinase		3 / 4
Cyclin-dependent kinase 2	CDK2	P24941	CHEMBL301	Kinase		1 / 17
Tyrosinase	TYR	P14679	CHEMBL1973	Oxidoreductase		2 / 3
Estradiol 17-beta-dehydrogenase 1	HSD17B1	P14061	CHEMBL3181	Enzyme		8 / 4
Aryl hydrocarbon receptor	AHR	P35869	CHEMBL3201	Transcription factor		1 / 1
Estrogen-related receptor alpha	ESRRA	P11474	CHEMBL3429	Nuclear receptor		2 / 2
Beta amyloid A4 protein	APP	P05067	CHEMBL2487	Membrane receptor		2 / 12
Poly [ADP-ribose] polymerase-1	PARP1	P09874	CHEMBL3105	Enzyme		3 / 9
Transferrin	TTR	P02766	CHEMBL3194	Secreted protein		2 / 2
Matrix metalloproteinase 12	MMP12	P39900	CHEMBL4393	Protease		1 / 1
Lymphocyte differentiation antigen CD38	CD38	P28907	CHEMBL4660	Enzyme		2 / 3
Aldo-keto reductase family 1 member B10	AKR1B10	O60218	CHEMBL5983	Enzyme		2 / 3
Tankyrase-2	TNKS2	Q9H2K2	CHEMBL6154	Enzyme		4 / 12
Tankyrase-1	TNKS	Q95271	CHEMBL6164	Enzyme		4 / 28
DNA topoisomerase I (by homology)	TOP1	P11387	CHEMBL1781	Isomerase		1 / 1
Telomerase reverse transcriptase	TERT	O14746	CHEMBL2916	Enzyme		9 / 22